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REVIEW

N-acetylcysteine in addiction management: current knowledge and future perspectives

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The efficacy of combined management of endometriosis-associated infertility

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Article Detail

Importance of medical and social factors in etiology of carious and non-carious diseases of children

Author: GAFFOROV S.A, YARIEVA O

Abstract: Dental diseases are the most common diseases in relation to other pathologies observed in the human body and damage to the hard tissue of the teeth - caries ranks first in frequency of occurrence. According to the results of epidemiological studies, the spread of caries varies from 70 percent to 90 percent. (15) and now there is no trend of decreasing. In addition, according to some authors. (17) Despite the fact that recently active preventive and curative procedures are underway, it's observed growth of disease rate day by day. The spread and intensity of caries depends on several factors they are: ecological and biogeochemical properties of the environment, socio-economic living conditions of the population, nutrition quality, level of health and level of medical knowledge of parents, organization of primary prevention in the region. (11;4;6;2;9) Many scientific studies have found that a number of factors such as the environment, production factors, climatic conditions, the microelement composition of the soil, water and air, the composition of food, living conditions significantly affect the occurrence and course of dental diseases, including carious and non-carious damage to solid dental tissue, diseases of the oral mucosa and inflammation of periodontal tissues. (5;7;16;10) In the human population it is very important to study the difference between the state and causes of dental diseases, for which reason the current state involves many diseases in the population. Modern social epidemiology changes from individual risk focus to multi-stage prospective. Treatment of patients with complaints of diseases of the oral cavity is a paradigm of social epidemiology, which makes it possible to pass the barriers that arise before us in considering the biological determinant of caries as a social determinant. The lack of objective data on the prevalence, structure of dental diseases, the peculiarity of clinical symptoms creates difficulties in scientifically-based formation of needs for special dental care, planning prevention of dental diseases in different age groups, implementation of the preventive basis of cases of neglect of parents' health. (3;12;1;13;14.). Based on the data of the social determinants of caries, it is possible to determine the demand for treatment and prophylactic measures for children and the amount of medical care necessary for the population. In view of the above, the examination of the present data is important.

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